

Teaching National Mentality of Allegoric Symbols on the Material of English and Uzbek Literature

Ubaydullayeva Durdonaxon ¹, Gulira'no Parpiyeva Xurshidjon Qizi ²

¹ Teacher of Ferghana State University

² Student of Ferghana State University, group 21.100 D

Abstract:

In this article hospitality as a linguistic-cultural concept has various semiotic (emblematic, allegorical and symbolic) signs. Emblematic features are based on communicative and verbal description, features of the manifestation of behavior in the lexicon of languages, allegorical features - the foreign meaning of this phenomenon in the languages under consideration, symbolic features - features describing the artistic understanding of this phenomenon in the linguistic cultures under consideration.[1]

Keywords: emblematic, linguistic-cultural semiotic, allegorical, communicative, behavioral, linguoculture.

Introduction

Linguistic-cultural and conceptual trends in contemporary linguistics in terms of identifying and revealing universal and national specific aspects is gaining relevance. According to many famous linguists, the concept is the world a part of the landscape, the value concepts of the entire linguistic community reflects, creates and emerges from culture. Language is the culture of the people and reflects the national mentality. Mental units are cultural and national understood through concepts. Both cultural and characteristic of the mentality of the Uzbek people.[2]

“Hospitality”, which is one of the national concepts, is also valued in the British nation. This concept is a “universal concept” between two peoples. The reason for studying hospitality as a concept is directly the people culture, its customs and values. How much culture if it is deep, it

leaves such a deep mark on the language. These “traces” are the lexicon of the language words and phrases, proverbs, wise words, expressions appears.[3]

Main body

The analysis was collected from the works of English and Uzbek writers in the novel genre based on examples. Abdulla Qadiri’s and Charlotte Bronte’s Jane Eyre and Somerset Maugham’s The Moon and Sixpence. The language of the concept of “hospitality” through examples collected from novels how it manifests itself in the speed was analyzed:

1. Lexical units used in the national environment of hospitality
2. Compatibility of the relationship between hospitality participants
3. expressive lexical units
4. Lexical units describing the guest and the host
5. Customs of welcoming guests and saying goodbye to them
6. Description of the hotel.

This is the nominative meaning of the concept of “hospitable / hospitality” in English is expressed in benevolent, friendly attitude towards strangers, guests: “They said we should stay another night, but I didn’t want to take advantage of their hospitality”. The metaphorical meaning of the concept of “Hospitable” is direct, thoughts and is to define the openness of actions in a general sense: “open to suggestions”, “receptive, open, ready or willing favorably.[4]

Proposals”: “hospitable to new ideas”. Emblematic of the concept of “hospitality” in these linguistic cultures sign is the use of various gastronomic symbols. So “tea” is an emblematic formula of inviting a dominant to a guest. In Uzbeks, “thank you for tea”, “let’s drink tea”, “over a cup of tea”, in English “come and have some tea”, “Will you come to tea tomorrow?” label as there are concepts of expressions. Tea ceremony as an element of hospitality plays an important role in life. And making tea and sharing it with guests is the sole authority of the host.[5]

Conclusion

Hospitality as a linguistic-cultural concept is a diverse semiotic (emblematic, allegorical and symbolic) symbols, which are being compared. The emblematic sign of the concept of “hospitality” in linguistic cultures is different is the use of different gastronomic symbols. Idioethnic signs - to semiotic signs includes symbols describing the field of communication, tonality and reference classification. English strict adherence to the rules of etiquette related to relations and status in the culture. If symbolic forms such as do are more dominant, the Uzbek culture of communication. The presentation model prevails, the rules of hospitality are the usual environment conforms to the standards: guest can come and go when they want, and has the right not to explain the reason for the visit.

References

1. Кибрик А.Ю. Моделирование языковой деятельности в интеллектуальных системах мах. – М., 1987. (280 с.)
2. Qodiriy A. “O’tgan kunlar” roman. T: Sharq, 2009. 400 b.
3. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary of Current English. Oxford: Russian Language Oxford University, 2007
4. Ундрицова М.В. Глуттонический дискурс: лингвокультурологические, когнитивно-прагматические и переводческие аспекты. Дисс.канд. филол. наук. – М.: 2015 – С. 13

5. Тер-Минасова С.Т. Язык и межкультурная коммуникация. М.: Слово / Слово, 2000. – 624 с.
6. Ubaydullayeva, Durdon, and Muhammadjon Tojiboyev. "TRANSLATION IS THE STUDY OF LINGUISTIC AND LITERARY." Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2023.
7. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). ҲОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ТИЛШУНОСЛИГИДА ҚЎШМА ГАПЛАР ТАВСИФИ, ТАСНИФИ ВА МЕТАТИЛИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. Science and innovation, 1(В6), 560-564.
8. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). PROBLEMS OF DESCRIPTION, CLASSIFICATION AND METATALOLOGY OF COMPLEX SENTENCES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS. Science and Innovation, 1(6), 560-564.
9. Ubaydullayeva, D., & Raxmonqulova, M. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA IJTIMOIIY YO'NALISHNING TARAQQIYOTI. Science and innovation, 1(В6), 869-873.
10. G'opporova, N., & Ubaydullayeva, D. (2022). A COMMUNICATIVE PRAGMATIC STUDY OF MEANS OF EXPRESSING DIRECTIVE SPEECH ACTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(12), 825-827.
11. Ubaydullayeva, D., & Raxmonqulova, M. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL DIRECTION IN LINGUISTICS. Science and Innovation, 1(6), 869-873.